

Behavioral impact of range anxiety and unlock fees on shared electric-moped usage

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Abstract

The evolving field of electric moped sharing systems is shaped by various determinants influencing user preferences, including range anxiety, pricing strategies, and regulatory changes. Utilizing a stated preference approach with a hybrid choice model, this research explores how these factors, along with attitudinal constructs, impact user decisions. The findings reveal that remaining range plays a critical role, with significant individual variability in its sensitivity, while perceived range anxiety did not significantly influence choices. Recent changes in helmet regulations have shifted preferences toward faster vehicles. Furthermore, dynamic pricing strategies, such as adjusting ride or unlock fees, can incentivize the use of less desirable vehicles with lower battery range or aid in user-based relocation. Nevertheless, low-range vehicles are less likely to be chosen, even with incentives. These insights provide valuable guidance for operators of electric moped sharing system to improve fleet management and optimize user satisfaction through strategic pricing and battery management.

Keywords: Electric Moped Sharing Systems, Shared Micromobility, Range Anxiety, Pricing, Hybrid Choice Model, Stated Preferences

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November 12, 2024

1. Introduction

As urban areas face growing challenges such as traffic congestion, pollution, and the environmental impact of private car ownership, shared electric mopeds (e-mopeds) emerge as a promising solution (Gössling 2020). These systems can reduce private car use, ease congestion, and lower both noise and greenhouse gas emissions, contributing to more sustainable and livable cities (Shaheen 2019). The free-floating type of shared e-mopeds (EMSS) have gained considerable popularity by offering users the flexibility of one-way transportation. However, this flexibility can lead to an imbalanced distribution of e-mopeds due to mismatches between supply and demand in both time and location (Ataç, Obrenović, and Bierlaire 2021). Consequently, the system may experience underutilization in low-demand areas and undersupply in high-demand areas. To address this challenge, various strategies can be employed from both supply-side and demand-side perspectives. Supply-side strategies, namely operator-based relocation, can be costly due to logistics and staff deployment expenses. Also, frequent operator-based relocation strategy have adverse environmental impact (Reis, Baptista, and Moura 2023). On the other hand, demand-side management strategies, specifically user-based relocation, may effectively mitigate this issue by offering (monetary) incentives to users for picking up vehicles with less desirable attributes (Angelopoulos et al. 2018; Pfrommer et al. 2014). The potential effectiveness of user-based relocation and overall service level enhancement relies on understanding users' preferences for individual e-mopeds, what they prioritize, and how to ensure the systems remain efficient, user-friendly, and accessible (Arbeláez Vélez 2024). Therefore, it is crucial for EMSS providers to identify key factors affecting users' choices and the trade-offs they make between these factors.

Studies have identified various factors affecting users' preferences toward individual e-moped usage, including pricing strategies and walking distance to access an e-moped (Chen, Fu, and Siao 2023; Loudon et al. 2023; Hoobroeckx et al. 2023), users' socio-demographic information (Kuijk et al. 2022), and behavioral determinants (Eccarius and Lu 2020). Previous studies on vehicle characteristics have mainly concentrated on either pricing strategies or their trade-offs with walking distances, often overlooking the crucial aspect of vehicle power level, an integral part of electric mobility systems. The understudied factor for shared

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3 electric vehicle services is the phenomenon of "range anxiety", the concern that the battery may deplete
4 before reaching the destination or a charging station (Nilsson 2014; Birrell, McGordon, and Jennings 2014).
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6 Range anxiety can be understood from two perspectives: objective perception, which refers to the trade-off
7 between the vehicle's remaining range and the trip distance, and attitudinal perception, reflecting how a
8 user's subjective experience and perceived stress in critical range situations influence their behavior (Nazari,
9 Mohammadian, and Stephens 2023; Shrestha et al. 2022). While most research on range anxiety has focused
10 on privately owned electric vehicles (BEVs), its effects on shared mobility services remain underexplored.
11 Compared to privately owned vehicles, shared micromobility systems such as e-mopeds and e-bikes add
12 additional layers of complexity that may heighten range anxiety. Factors such as diverse vehicle types,
13 limited user experience, insufficient information on routes or battery levels, and the inability to initiate
14 charging can amplify user concerns. Consequently, users may avoid vehicles with lower battery levels, even
15 when the remaining range is sufficient for their trip. This perception can create inefficiencies for operators
16 and reduce the perceived availability of vehicles.
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30 Study by (Loudon et al. 2023) has shown that individuals with prior experience using shared mopeds
31 value e-moped attributes differently compared to those without such experience. In this study, we examine
32 prior moped usage as a latent variable alongside subjective range anxiety. Additionally, new regulations
33 have shown an impact on user preferences (Gössling 2020). With the introduction of helmet regulations for
34 e-mopeds in the Netherlands (commenced on January 2023), helmet use is mandatory for all types of e-
35 mopeds, whereas previously, helmets were only required for faster vehicle types (Rijksoverheid 2022). These
36 regulatory changes are expected to affect user behavior and preferences, emphasizing the need to consider
37 both attitudinal factors and external regulations in understanding the user's preferences towards individual
38 e-mopeds.
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49 This study investigates the factors influencing individual vehicle choice in EMSS, with a particular
50 emphasis on vehicle battery level and the trade-offs between unlock fees, per-minute ride fees, and walking
51 time required to access an e-moped. Utilizing a Hybrid Choice Modeling approach, we explore the impact of
52 range anxiety in EMSS on user preferences, addressing both the objective remaining battery range and the
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3 attitudinal factors that influence behavior in critical range situations. Additionally, this study examines the
4 impact of previous usage and regulatory changes to have a comprehensive view of user preferences. These
5 areas have not been extensively covered in existing literature, highlighting the novelty and relevance of our
6 analysis.
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11 The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the relevant literature. Section 3
12 describes the design of the stated preference experiment, the survey design, and the data collection process.
13 The methodology for the choice modeling framework and its application are described in Section 4. The
14 modeling results are presented and discussed in Section 5, followed by the model application in Section 6.
15 Section 7 discusses management insights for EMSS providers, along with limitations and suggestions for
16 future research. Finally, the paper concludes in Section 8.
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26 **2. Literature Review**

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28 Next to other mobility sharing modes, shared e-moped services have emerged over the last decade, with
29 their uptake accelerating significantly in recent years (Aguilera-García, Gomez, and Sobrino 2020). EMSS
30 currently operate fleets of free-floating e-mopeds that can be selected, unlocked, and locked via an app,
31 charging users on a per-minute basis along with a fixed unlock fee. Recent studies show that adoption of
32 e-moped sharing services is more prevalent among specific socio-demographic groups, including younger to
33 middle-aged adults, males, highly educated individuals, and those with higher incomes (Aguilera-García,
34 Gomez, and Sobrino 2020; Vega-Gonzalo et al. 2024). Also, users with prior experience using EMSS are more
35 likely to continue utilizing these services compared to those without such experience (Chen, Fu, and Siao
36 2023). While some factors driving EMSS adoption and usage have been identified, a more comprehensive
37 understanding is necessary to fully capture the complexities involved.
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50 Understanding main drivers of e-moped usage is essential for addressing spatial-temporal imbalances
51 caused by uneven demand patterns through user-based relocation strategies. Several studies have demon-
52 strated the potential of user-based relocation strategies in shared micromobility systems (Pfrommer et al.
53 2014; Neijmeijer et al. 2020). Two main factors determining users' willingness to participate in relocation
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3 strategies are identified in the literature: the willingness to walk for a prolonged period and the correspond-
4 ing reduction in ride fees (J. Wang and Y. Wang 2021). Neijmeijer et al. 2020 conducted the first case study
5 applying a dynamic pricing strategy in a free-floating e-moped sharing system, finding that even minor price
6 deviations can effectively alter travel patterns. However, their analysis was limited to aggregate system
7 performance metrics, overlooking individual behaviors and vehicle characteristics. Hoobroeckx et al. 2023
8 utilized Multinomial Logit models to examine the individual users' trade-offs between per-minute ride fees
9 and walking distance based on stated preference survey data from the Netherlands. Their findings indicate
10 that users require a reduction of €0.02 per minute in ride fees for each additional minute of walking to access
11 a vehicle. Also, Chen, Fu, and Siao 2023 explored individual preferences in e-moped sharing by incorporating
12 latent variables (advocacy for the service, hedonic motivation, and attitudes toward the service), capturing a
13 better interpretation of user preferences in Taiwan. While these studies provide valuable insights into under-
14 standing of users preferences of EMSS, they do not account for vehicle battery levels—an integral attribute
15 of electric mobility systems that influences both system efficiency and user decision-making. Integrating
16 vehicle-specific characteristics with user behavior could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the
17 dynamics within EMSS and enhance the effectiveness of user-based relocation strategies.

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35 Subjective Range anxiety captures how personal attitudes and anxiety related to low battery levels
36 influence the likelihood of choosing an e-moped, providing deeper insights into user behavior, preferences,
37 and potential barriers to adoption (Vij and Walker 2016). While range anxiety has been extensively studied
38 in battery electric vehicles (BEVs), it remains underexplored in shared micromobility systems. Research on
39 BEVs, such as studies by Rauh, Franke, and Krems (2015) and Franke, Günther, et al. (2015), identified
40 the available range safety buffer as a key factor influencing range anxiety. From this framework, two critical
41 factors emerge that influence user preferences in situations of limited range: the remaining objective battery
42 range (actual distance the vehicle can cover) and the subjective point of range anxiety (stress threshold based
43 on perceived range insufficiency). These factors are crucial in shaping user behavior and satisfaction in low-
44 range scenarios. In shared micromobility systems, range anxiety may be triggered at higher remaining ranges
45 compared to BEVs due to increased uncertainties and users' limited experience with shared vehicles in critical
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3 range situations. Key mitigation strategies include reducing uncertainties and providing comprehensive
4 information (Rainieri, Buizza, and Ghilardi 2023). Furthermore, the trade-offs faced by users in shared
5 electric mobility systems differ from those in privately owned BEVs. In BEVs, trade-offs typically involve
6 route choice and charging infrastructure availability, whereas in shared systems, users can opt for vehicles
7 with higher remaining ranges, disregarding those perceived as having insufficient range. These distinctions
8 underscore the necessity to study critical range situations in shared electric mobility systems, focusing on
9 both objective factors like remaining battery range and subjective factors such as perceived range anxiety.
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12 Despite the valuable insights provided by existing studies on shared e-moped adoption, there remains a
13 lack of comprehensive assessment regarding vehicle battery levels, service attributes—including both unlock
14 and per-minute ride fees—as well as users’ attitudes (such as range anxiety and previous system usage)
15 and regulatory changes influencing usage behavior. By integrating these factors, this study aims to capture
16 unobserved heterogeneity, improve model estimation performance, and enhance behavioral interpretation
17 (Abou-Zeid and Ben-Akiva 2024). Utilizing a Hybrid Choice Model, this research explores the interplay of
18 these attitudinal factors, aiming to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the user’s preference for
19 individual e-moped usage in the EMSS.
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36 **3. Survey design and data collection**

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39 This section provides a comprehensive overview of the survey and data collection process. The final
40 survey questionnaire consists of two parts: The stated preference choice experiment and questions about
41 the socio-demographic profiles of the users, as well as indicator questions related to latent variables. These
42 components are explained in the following. Additionally, the data collection process is described, outlining
43 the methodology used to gather responses and ensure the validity of the data.
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51 *3.1. Stated Preference Experiment*

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53 A stated preference (SP) approach is selected because it allows the simulation of decision making by
54 presenting respondents with hypothetical but realistic scenarios (Louviere et al. 2000). The key components
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3 of the SP experiment are outlined here, including the context of the survey, the attributes, their respective
4 levels, and finally the process of generating the choice sets.
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7 8 *3.1.1. Context of the trip* 9

10 The choice scenarios are designed within a fixed context to create critical range situations. As trip motive,
11 running an errand is because such trips are typically occasional and time-sensitive, unlike daily commutes
12 or leisurely trips (Loudon et al. 2023). A 5-km travel distance is chosen based on Hoobroeckx et al. (2023),
13 which found that trips up to 5 km increase the utility of EMSS use, with the 90th percentile of trips being
14 under 7.5 km and the average around 4 km. This translates to an approximate riding time of 15 minutes.
15 This fixed distance emphasizes the importance of remaining range while still reflecting typical EMSS trip
16 lengths. Weather conditions were standardized to neutral values (17°C, cloudy and dry) to minimize their
17 influence.
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27 28 *3.1.2. Attributes and Attribute levels* 29

30 In the stated preference experiment, five key vehicle attributes were considered: walking distance to the
31 vehicle in minutes, unlock fee in €, ride fee in € per minute, remaining driving (that represents remaining
32 battery level of the e-moped) range in kilometers, and e-moped type (25km/h or 45km/h). These attributes
33 were chosen as they are the main factors displayed to users on the app interfaces of the EMSS providers.
34 However, it is important to note that the remaining driving range has previously not been included in EMSS
35 literature. The study therefore aims to explore the role that this attribute could play in influencing user
36 preferences, particularly in critical range situations. Table 1 indicates a complete list of attributes, their
37 attribute levels, and the corresponding indicator for the estimation.
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47 The attribute levels are determined based on various sources, including current market situations and
48 previous research. The levels of walking distance are derived from the data collected by Hoobroeckx et al.
49 (2023), who report that the 90th percentile of walking distances is below 550 meters. Assuming an average
50 walking speed of 4 km/h, this translates to just over 8 minutes of walking time. Including some buffers,
51 the walking times for this experiment range from 1 to 10 minutes. The unlock fee, ride fee, and vehicle
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Table 1: Attributes and Attribute Levels for the stated preference experiment

Attribute	Attribute Levels	Parameter Indicator
walking distance in minutes	1,4,7,10	$b_{Distance}$
unlock fee in €	0.5,1,1.5,2	$b_{UnlockFee}$
ride fee in €/minute	0.27,0.30,0.33,0.36	$b_{RideFee}$
remaining driving range in km	5,8,11,14	$b_{Battery}$
vehicle type (dummy coded)	25km/h (1), 45km/h (0)	$b_{VehicleType}$

types reflect the current market situation of EMSS providers, with at least one level above and below the current market situation. The levels for the remaining driving range are chosen to confront participants with critical range situations, providing a realistic context for the experiment. The lowest level represents the distance of the trip, and the three levels offer different margins of range buffers. As no prior research has been conducted on the influence of critical range situations, a broad range of remaining battery levels is selected, extending up to nearly three times the required trip length. It is assumed that all levels of remaining range still fall within the category of critical range situations. For the remainder of this paper, all discussions on critical range situations refer to this definition. Additional specific attributes introduced in this study include the unlock fee and the remaining driving range, both critical to understanding user preferences in EMSS by reflecting the current market situation and practical challenges faced by users.

3.1.3. Generation of choice sets

The construction of the choice sets in this SP experiment is designed to capture the key vehicle attributes. The survey includes a total of 16 choice sets, each presenting 2 e-moped alternatives to the participants, and one option not to use the sharing service (opt-out option). All attributes varied between the choice sets to ensure a comprehensive analysis of user preferences. Figure 1 represents an example choice set.

	Opt-out		
Distance to vehicle in walking minutes	7 min	4 min	-
Unlock fee in €	1.5 €	1 €	-
Price per minute in €/min	0.33 €/min	0.30 €/min	-
Remaining battery range in km	8 km	11 km	-
Vehicle type	45 km/h	25 km/h	-

Figure 1: Example Choice Set from Survey

A D-efficient design is used to construct the choice sets using Ngene software (ChoiceMetrics 2012), with priors from the pilot survey to enhance statistical efficiency. The survey is divided into four blocks of four choice sets, meaning each participant answers four choice sets. The blocks are randomly presented to participants, ensuring that all four blocks are equally distributed. The choice sets are generated twice: initially for the pilot survey and then revised based on the pilot results for the main data collection. This iterative process refines the choice sets, ensuring they are both realistic and effective in capturing the necessary data to analyze user preferences. The final construction of the choice sets achieves a D-error of 0.214.

To ensure realism and relevance, certain constraints are applied. The distribution of the remaining driving range attribute is adjusted, with the 5 km level appearing more frequently and the 14 km level less frequently. The vehicle type attribute is dummy-coded for analysis, where 1 represents the 25 km/h version and 0 represents the 45 km/h version. Including an opt-out option in the SP experiment increases its explanatory power by enhancing the realism and validity of the decision-making process (Louviere et al. 2000). The opt-out option captures situations where respondents might choose not to make a decision, providing valuable insights into their preferences and allowing for the modeling of latent variables or socio-demographic influences on EMSS use (Dhar and Simonson 2003).

3.2. Explanatory variables

To enhance the explanatory power of the stated preference experiment, two latent variables are included in the survey: respondents' attitudes towards EMSS and their perception of range anxiety, representing the subjective influence of critical range situations on user preferences. Incorporating these latent constructs allows us to measure the impact of psychological factors on decision-making beyond observable attributes like cost or remaining range. For example, attitudes towards EMSS reveal how positive or negative perceptions affect willingness to use them, consistent with studies conducted in Spain by Aguilera-García, Gomez, and Sobrino (2020) and Aguilera-García, Gomez, Sobrino, and Vinagre Díaz (2021). Similarly, adding an attitudinal construct to better understand the influence of range anxiety, beyond the objective remaining range attribute, enriches our understanding of how critical range situations affect user preferences. The latent variables are measured using multiple questions, with responses recorded on a 5-point Likert scale. A complete overview of the survey questions and descriptive statistics is presented in Table 2 in Section 5.1. Although the target respondents for this study are individuals above 18 years of age with a valid driving license, a variety of socio-demographic characteristics and information about prior use are also collected and incorporated into the modeling process. These socio-demographic attributes, providing deeper insights into respondents' backgrounds and preferences, are detailed in Section 5.1.

3.3. Data collection process

The survey focuses on the Netherlands without targeting any specific region, ensuring broad applicability of the findings. The target respondents are EMSS users and non-users aged 18 and older with a valid driver's license, capturing a wide range of user preferences. A pilot survey is conducted prior to the main data collection to ensure clarity and enhance the robustness of the choice sets. The reliability of the latent variable indicators is also tested based on the pilot results and adjusted accordingly. The final survey is launched on May 27, 2024, and remains open until July 24, 2024. The distribution strategy involves three main channels: social media platforms (e.g., LinkedIn), mailing lists, and flyer handouts at micromobility hubs.

4. Choice Modeling Framework

We adopt a hybrid choice model (HCM) or integrated choice and latent variable (ICLV) model with random parameter estimation. This model allows us to simultaneously investigate the effects of vehicle attributes, socio-demographic factors, and latent attitudes on the intention to use EMSS (Danthurebandara, Vandebroek, and Yu 2013). In the next section the underlying assumptions and structure of the HCM are explained.

4.1. Hybrid Choice Model with random parameter estimation

The HCM enhances traditional discrete choice models by integrating latent variables and socio-demographic factors, offering a more comprehensive understanding of individual preferences and behaviors (Ben-Akiva et al. 2002). A key advantage of HCM is its ability to capture unobservable factors, such as attitudes and perceptions, through psychometric data and structural equation modeling. This allows for a nuanced analysis of how these latent traits, alongside observed factors such as vehicle attributes, shape decision-making (Bolduc and Daziano 2010).

The choice probability for the HCM is based on utility maximization theory, and the formula is given by:

$$P_{ij} = \int \frac{e^{V_{ij}(\beta, \eta)}}{\sum_{k \in C_i} e^{V_{ik}(\beta, \eta)}} f(\beta, \eta | \theta) d\beta d\eta \quad (1)$$

Where:

- P_{ij} is the choice probability of alternative j by individual i .
- C_i is the set of all alternatives available to individual i .
- β represents the vector of random parameters.
- η represents the vector of latent variables.
- $f(\beta, \eta | \theta)$ is the joint density function of β and η with parameters θ .

Two latent variables for attitudes towards e-mopeds and perception of range anxiety were included in the model. In addition to the latent variables, the model incorporates random parameters, when found significant, through an iterative backward model estimation procedure. This approach involved testing all vehicle attributes and retaining only those as random that were statistically significant at the confidence level 95% for their corresponding estimates. Figure 2 represents the complete conceptual model of the HCM.

Figure 2: Conceptual Model HCM for e-moped usage

The utility functions for the two e-moped alternatives are identical and defined in Equation 2. The utility for the opt-out option is set to 0 to represent the baseline utility as described in Equation 3:

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_{e_Moped} = & ASC_{MSS} + b_{Distance} \cdot Distance + b_{UnlockFee} \cdot LockFee + b_{RideFee} \cdot RideFee + \\
 & b_{Battery} \cdot RemainingRange + b_{VehicleType} \cdot VehicleType + \\
 & b_{previous} \cdot PreviousUse + b_{bike} \cdot Bike + b_{low_income} \cdot IncomeLow + \\
 & b_{alone} \cdot LivingAlone + b_{shared} \cdot LivingShared + \\
 & \eta_{emop} \cdot Attitude_E_mop + \eta_{rangaxi} \cdot Perception_range_anxiety
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

$$V_{Opt.Out} = 0 \quad (3)$$

The socio-demographic variables are included directly in the utility function rather than being associated with latent variables. This decision was made to observe the direct effects of socio-demographics on EMSS utility, enabling a clear understanding of how factors such as income, living situation, and previous use immediately influence user choices. This approach facilitates more straightforward comparisons with previous studies that have similarly examined the influence of socio-demographics on EMSS such as Aguilera-García, Gomez, and Sobrino (2020) and Hoobroeckx et al. (2023).

Unlike typical latent variable models that use observed socio-demographic variables to explain latent attitudes, this model focuses solely on the latent attitudes themselves, without linking them directly to observed socio-demographics. Incorporating socio-demographic variables in the utility function and latent variables would increase model complexity, which could lead to convergence issues, less robust parameter estimates, or multicollinearity (Ben-Akiva et al. 2002).

The latent variable integration is done using a set of adapted structural equations (Equation 4) and measurement equations (Equation 5), as explained below.

$$\eta_l = \epsilon_l \quad (4)$$

Where, η_l is the l -th latent variable (e.g., attitudes towards e-mopeds, perceived range anxiety) and ϵ_l is the disturbance term associated with the latent variable η_l . In this model, since no observed socio-demographic variables are used to explain the latent variables, the structural equation consists only of this error term. The latent variables are estimated directly from the survey indicators, capturing the psychological dimensions relevant to choice behavior.

$$I_q = \zeta_q \cdot \eta_l + \delta_q \quad (5)$$

Where I_q is the q -th indicator, representing survey questions measuring attitudes towards e-mopeds or

perceived range anxiety. ζ_q is the loading factor, indicating the strength of the relationship between the latent variable η_l and the indicator I_q and δ_q is the random error term for indicator I_q , assumed to follow a standard normal distribution.

The HCM was estimated using 5000 Halton draws for the random parameters and the error terms of the latent variables to ensure efficient and accurate integration over the random components. Unlike pseudo-random numbers, which are completely random, Halton sequences are designed to cover the integration space more evenly. This even distribution helps reduce the simulation error associated with maximum simulated likelihood estimation (Zeng 2016). As an estimation software, the Apollo package in R was used (Hess and Palma 2019).

4.2. Model application framework

To further contextualize the results, we employ two methods: the calculation of Willingness-to-Pay (WTP) indicators and a scenario analysis to assess market shares for different vehicle attribute values.

4.2.1. WTP Indicators

We calculated WTP indicators for all non-price vehicle attributes (walking distance, remaining range, and vehicle type) to quantify the trade-offs users are willing to make between various vehicle features. Traditionally, WTP indicators are calculated by dividing the estimated coefficient of a non-price attribute by the coefficient of a price attribute. However, in our model, we have two price components: the unlock fee and the per-minute ride fee, resulting in two distinct sets of WTP indicators. For example, the WTP for a reduction in walking time based on the unlock fee can be calculated using the formula:

$$WTP_{\text{Distance, UnlockFee}} = \frac{b_{\text{Distance}}}{b_{\text{UnlockFee}}} \quad (6)$$

where b_{distance} is the estimated coefficient for the walking distance to access the e-moped, and $b_{\text{unlock fee}}$ is the estimated coefficient for the unlock fee. Since both coefficients are fixed parameters in our model, this WTP is a single value. However, for attributes with random coefficients, such as the per-minute ride fee and

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3 remaining battery range, the WTP indicators are calculated using distributions. For instance, the WTP for
4 additional battery range (driving range) based on the per-minute ride fee is determined by:

$$5 \quad WTP_{\text{Battery, RideFee}} = \frac{b_{\text{Battery}}}{b_{\text{RideFee}}} \quad (7)$$

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12 In this case, b_{battery} and $b_{\text{ride fee}}$ are random parameters that follow specific distributions. To calculate
13 the WTP, we derive the distribution of their ratio as shown in Equation 7, which represents the range of
14 WTP values across different individuals. This approach captures the variability in user sensitivity to these
15 attributes and reflects the heterogeneity in the population, providing a more comprehensive understanding
16 of user preferences. The results of these indicators are discussed in Section 6.1.
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24 *4.2.2. Scenario Analysis*

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26 For the scenario analysis, we utilize the choice probability function of the HCM to explore how variations
27 in vehicle attributes affect user choices. Unlike typical scenario analyses that use fixed values for each
28 scenario, this approach examined a range of attribute values to capture their dynamic influence on the
29 likelihood of EMSS usage. Heatmap figures in Section 6.2, are generated to visually represent how changes
30 in attributes like walking distance, and remaining range, compared to the price attributes, impact the
31 probability of choosing EMSS. Since the two e-moped alternatives have identical utilities in this analysis, we
32 treated them as a single alternative, focusing on the decision to choose any e-moped versus opting out. This
33 approach simplifies the analysis by combining the two e-mopeds, allowing us to concentrate on how different
34 vehicle attributes affect the overall likelihood of choosing EMSS. To further simplify the calculation, we
35 used mean values instead of random parameters. This is done to ensure a clearer illustration of the general
36 trends in the heatmaps. Taking into account these assumptions, the probability function for choosing an
37 e-moped can be expressed as follows:
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$$53 \quad P_{\text{E-Moped}}(i, j) = \frac{\exp(V_{\text{E-Moped}}(i, j))}{1 + \exp(V_{\text{E-Moped}}(i, j))} \quad (8)$$

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3 where i represents different levels of a price attribute (per-minute ride fee and unlock fee) and j represents
4 different levels of a non-price attribute (walking time, vehicle type, remaining range). The results of this
5 analysis are presented in Section 6.2.
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10 11 **5. Results**

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13 The following sections provide an overview of the results derived from the choice model and survey. First,
14 the descriptive statistics of the respondents are presented. Then, as discussed in the methodology (Section
15 4), the HCM with a random parameter approach and the derived indicators are discussed.
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21 *5.1. Descriptive Statistics*

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23 This section provides a brief overview of the characteristics of the respondents. Of the 154 respondents,
24 133 completed the entire survey and met the criteria for the SP experiment, which required participants to
25 be over 18 years old and possess a valid driving license. This resulted in a total of 532 observations collected.
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29 The distribution of users and non-users was nearly equal, with 49.6% of respondents being non-users,
30 7.5% being one-time users, 36% having used EMSS a few times, and 6.9% being frequent users. Age-wise,
31 the sample is skewed towards younger individuals, with 66% of respondents under 30 and 86% under 40.
32 Although this may present bias, it aligns with the demographic of the primary user of EMSS, as reported by
33 numerous studies, such as Aguilera-García, Gomez, and Sobrino (2020). The gender distribution was slightly
34 biased towards male respondents, which comprised 58% of the sample, while female respondents accounted
35 for 40%. An additional 2% of respondents selected a third gender or preferred not to disclose their gender.
36 The majority of the respondents were employed (57%) or students (33%), with smaller percentages being
37 self-employed, looking for work, or retired. For the income distribution, respondents can be categorized into
38 three income groups: low, middle and high. Low-income respondents, earning up to €2000, make up 39.1%
39 of the sample. The middle-income group, earning between €2000-4000, comprises 42.8% of the respondents,
40 while the high-income group, earning above €4000, represents 16.8% of the sample. The living situations
41 were also categorized into three groups: living alone, living with a partner, and living in shared flats. Those
42 living alone made up 21.8% of the sample, while 46% lived with a partner, and 30.8% lived in shared flats.
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3 Regarding education levels, a substantial proportion of respondents had a high educational level: 57% had
4 a master's degree or Ph.D., and another 36% had a bachelor's degree.
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7 Compared to national averages in the Netherlands, respondents in this study were younger, more edu-
8 cated, and had a slight male bias. In terms of income, the sample was more skewed toward low to middle
9 incomes, with 39.1% earning up to €2000 and 42.8% earning between €2000-4000, while the national income
10 distribution has a more balanced spread across different brackets (CBS 2022). These differences, particularly
11 in age and education, are expected as younger, more educated individuals tend to be early adopters of new
12 mobility technologies like EMSS (Aguilera-García, Gomez, and Sobrino 2020).
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20 The latent variables "Attitude toward EMSS" and "Perceived Range Anxiety" were designed to capture
21 the underlying psychological factors that influence user preferences in vehicle choice within EMSS. Each
22 latent variable was measured using a set of four indicators. For "Attitude Towards EMSS," the indicators
23 included statements about e-mopeds being a good addition to urban transport, their convenience, their
24 potential to reduce private vehicle use, and their ease of access. Meanwhile, "Perceived Range Anxiety"
25 was assessed through indicators focusing on concerns about the remaining driving range, anxiety due to low
26 battery levels, users' estimations of trip length, and preferences for higher range to avoid stress. Respondents
27 rated these indicators on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree." An
28 overview of the descriptive statistics for the latent variables can be seen in Table 2.
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Table 2: Descriptive Statistics and Reliability for Latent Variable Indicators

Indicator Description		Frequency Distribution (%)						
No	Attitude Towards EMSS ($\alpha = 0.735$)	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5
1	E-Moped Sharing Systems are a good addition to the various modes of transport available in urban regions	3.95	0.84	0.8	3.8	13.5	56.4	25.6
2	E-Moped Sharing Systems are a convenient and practical mode of transport in urban regions	3.92	0.84	0.8	3.8	13.5	56.4	25.6
3	E-Moped Sharing Systems can reduce your need for a private vehicle/car	3.51	1.18	3.8	11.3	18.8	41.4	24.8
4	E-Moped Sharing Systems are easy to use/access	3.79	0.82	0.8	8.3	15.8	55.6	19.5
Perceived Range Anxiety ($\alpha = 0.658$)								
5	When choosing an e-moped, the remaining driving range of the vehicle is important to me.	3.81	0.90	2.3	6.0	14.3	55.6	21.8
6	I experience anxiety while using an e-moped from a sharing system due to low remaining driving range.	3.26	1.03	3.8	20.3	30.8	28.6	16.5
7	I do have an approximation of the trip length when taking an e-moped.	3.68	0.92	1.5	8.3	22.6	47.4	20.3
8	To avoid anxiety or stress, I would choose an e-moped with significantly more range than necessary.	3.59	1.10	3.0	11.3	21.1	44.4	20.3

The descriptive statistics for the latent variable indicators reveal several key insights. For "Attitude Towards EMSS," the indicators generally show high mean values, particularly for Indicator numbers 1, 2, and 4. This suggests a favorable overall perception of e-mopeds among respondents. The reliability coefficient Cronbach alpha suggests good internal consistency with a value of 0.735. Cronbach's alpha values above 0.7 are generally considered acceptable for measuring the reliability of a latent variable (J. Gliem and R. Gliem 2003). On the other hand, "Perceived Range Anxiety" indicators have more varied responses, as reflected by their wider range of mean values. The concern about remaining driving range (indicator number 6) shows a relatively high mean, indicating that it is a significant factor for many users. While the reported Cronbach alpha is slightly below the desired threshold of 0.7, when excluding indicator number 7, which has

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3 the least explanatory power for the latent variable, Cronbach’s alpha increases to 0.8049, indicating strong
4 reliability. This can be justified, as indicator number 7 has the lowest factor loading from the latent variable
5 and is further not included in the final latent variable estimation, as it showed no significant influence on
6 the variable (see Section 5.3).
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11 12 5.2. Hybrid Choice Model

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14 In the following, the results of the HCM are discussed and interpreted. With the utility of not using
15 EMSS fixed at zero, an Alternative Specific Constant (ASC_{MSS}) was estimated representing the base utility
16 of choosing EMSS. Furthermore, the model reveals how various socio-demographic factors and attitudes, such
17 as range anxiety or perceptions of shared mobility, impact the likelihood of selecting EMSS. As discussed in
18 Section 4 an iterative backward estimation process was adopted, only retaining significant socio-demographic
19 variables and latent indicators as well as, testing for heterogeneity through a random coefficient distribution.
20 The main estimates for the vehicle attributes, socio-demographics and latent variables are presented in Table
21 3. The full set of parameter estimates can be found in Appendix B. The following section will analyze and
22 interpret these results to provide a comprehensive understanding of the model results and implications.
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34 All estimated attribute parameters show high statistical significance, with all t-ratios surpassing the
35 critical value of 1.96. This threshold corresponds to the 95% confidence level. Thus allowing us to reject the
36 null hypothesis that the parameter mean effect is equal to zero. The alternative specific constant ASC_{MSS}
37 for EMSS is positive. The value of ASC_{MSS} represents the systematic difference in utility between choosing
38 the EMSS alternative and opting for the opt-out alternative when the EMSS attribute values are set to
39 zero. This suggests a systematic preference for the EMSS option over the opt-out alternatives, independent
40 of other model attributes. This is contrary to previous findings by Hoobroeckx et al. (2023) indicating a
41 negative base utility for EMSS. This change may be explained by varying context attributes in the latter
42 study presenting less favorable conditions to potential users.
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53 The newly introduced pricing parameter for the unlock fee ($b_{UnlockFee}$) showed the expected negative
54 sign with an estimate of -1.42, indicating a general disutility for higher unlock fees. While this parameter
55 is included for the first time in an SP-experiment on EMSS in the Netherlands this is expected and in line
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Table 3: Estimation Results Hybrid Choice Model

Model Fit Indicators				
Metric	Value			
LL(start)	-2421.42			
LL(final, whole model)	-1410.67			
BIC	3075.63			
Vehicle Attributes				
Parameter	Estimate	s.e.	t-ratio	p-value
ASC_{MSS}	10.727	1.784	6.014	0.000
$b_{UnlockFee}$	-1.419	0.223	-6.364	0.000
$b_{VehicleType}$	-1.023	0.211	-4.839	0.000
$b_{Distance}$	-0.340	0.043	-7.941	0.000
Random Parameter	Estimate (s.d.)	s.e.	t-ratio	p-value
$b_{RideFee}$	-25.677 (9.079)	0.127	-	-
$b_{Battery}$	0.271 (0.0786)	0.001	-	-
Socio-Demographic Estimates				
$b_{previous}$	-1.537	0.599	-2.565	0.005
b_{bike}	-2.258	1.115	-2.025	0.022
b_{alone}	1.197	0.463	2.586	0.005
b_{shared}	-0.814	0.438	-1.859	0.032
b_{low_income}	-1.166	0.455	-2.562	0.005
Latent Variable Parameter Estimates				
η_{emop}	0.956	0.339	2.823	0.003
$\eta_{rangaxi}$	-0.314	0.321	-0.978	0.164

with recent studies on micromobility (Ren et al. 2024), also reporting the negative influence of unlock fees on user preference. The parameter for the walking distance to a vehicle ($b_{Distance}$) also has its expected negative sign with an estimate of -0.34 indicating general disutility for longer walking distances.

The negative parameter for vehicle type ($b_{VehicleType}$) indicates a preference against the slower vehicle, which contrasts with the findings of Hoobroeckx et al. (2023). According to Hoobroeckx et al. (2023), one of the key reasons users opted for the slower vehicle was the absence of the new helmet requirement. The current model suggests that these new regulations have shifted user preference towards faster vehicles.

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3 Additionally, the remaining advantage of using bike paths with the slower vehicle type does not offer a
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5 sufficient incentive for users to prefer it over the faster alternative.
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8 The two parameters that showed significant heterogeneity in the estimation is the second pricing pa-
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10 rameter for the per-minute ride fee ($b_{RideFee}$) and the parameter for the remaining driving range ($b_{Battery}$).
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12 All other parameters have also been tested for heterogeneity but did not show significant variability. We
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14 assumed negative and positive log normal distribution for the per-minute ride fee and battery level respec-
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16 tively, based on empirical modeling practices grounded in their behavioral properties (Train 2009). The
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18 parameter estimate for the ride fee ($b_{RideFee}$) shows a mean value of -25.68 with a standard deviation of 9.1.
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20 This results in the 95% quantile of the distribution between -46.75 and -11.996 (see Figure 3a). While we
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22 can see a high influence of the ride fee on perceived user utility this factor varies greatly between individuals.
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24 The newly introduced parameter estimate for the remaining driving range ($b_{Battery}$) has a mean value of
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26 0.271 with a standard deviation of 0.079. This results in the 95% quantile of the distribution between 0.149
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28 and 0.454 (see Figure 3b). This suggests that higher battery levels generally increase the vehicle’s utility,
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30 but there is substantial variability in how different users value this attribute. Some users may have a strong
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32 preference for higher battery levels to avoid range anxiety, while others may be less concerned. This finding
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34 indicates that range anxiety is greatly influenced by psychological factors as well as the user’s skills.
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Figure 3: Distributions of random parameter estimates

5.3. Influence of Latent Variables and Socio-Demographics

The influence of socio-demographic characteristics showed significance in only 5 parameters. The "previous use" parameter unexpectedly had a negative sign, indicating that prior experience with EMSS negatively influences the likelihood of using it. This contrasts with findings from studies by Aguilera-García, Gomez,

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3 and Sobrino (2020) and Alonso-González et al. (2021), which reported that previous use is one of the main
4 factors driving EMSS adoption. This discrepancy can be explained by the context of this study, as users
5 with previous experience demonstrate lower utility for using EMSS within the given context of the study.
6
7 This divergence indicates that the utility derived from previous use of EMSS diminishes under certain (unfa-
8 vorable) operational conditions or constraints. In line with previous research (Hoobroeckx et al. 2023), bike
9 ownership negatively influences EMSS usage, suggesting a significant overlap in the use patterns between
10 bike trips and EMSS. Interestingly, respondents' living situations also impact EMSS usage. Living alone
11 has a positive influence on EMSS adoption, while living in a shared flat negatively influences it, compared
12 to living with a partner, which serves as the reference category. Lastly, lower income negatively impacts
13 EMSS usage compared to higher incomes, while the medium income category did not show significance
14 and was therefore excluded from the model. As discussed in the review of the literature of this study, the
15 influence of higher income on EMSS adoption is not consistent within previous studies, sometimes driving
16 adaptations, sometimes hindering it (Aguilera-García, Gomez, and Sobrino 2020; Vega-Gonzalo et al. 2024).
17 To summarize these findings within this stated preference context, users with high income, no previous use,
18 and who live alone are most likely to use EMSS.
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35 In the final HCM, three out of four indicators for both "Attitude towards EMSS" and "Perceived Range
36 Anxiety" showed statistical significance, demonstrating the relevance of these latent variables in capturing
37 user preferences. The parameter η_{emop} for "Attitude Towards EMSS" was estimated at 0.956 with a robust
38 t-ratio of 2.991, indicating that a positive attitude towards EMSS increases the likelihood of choosing an
39 EMSS over opting out. This suggests that users with favorable perceptions of e-mopeds are more likely
40 to adopt EMSS, and is in line with previous studies like Chen, Fu, and Siao (2023) and Aguilera-García,
41 Gomez, Sobrino, and Vinagre Díaz (2021). Conversely, the parameter $\eta_{rangaxi}$ for "Perceived Range Anxiety"
42 is estimated at -0.314 with a robust t-ratio of -0.986, indicating that higher range anxiety negatively impacts
43 the decision to use EMSS. Although this estimate is not statistically significant, it suggests the potential
44 influence that subjective perception of range anxiety has on user preferences. This implies that users more
45 concerned about battery depletion are less inclined to choose EMSS.
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3 The low and insignificant impact for the attitudinal factor of range anxiety can be explained by the
4 inclusion of a second parameter estimate in this research, which refers to the objective perception of range
5 anxiety: the remaining driving range. This parameter is estimated as a random parameter, which captures
6 individual heterogeneity but may also reduce the explanatory power of other fixed parameters (McFadden
7 and Train 2000). Furthermore, previous research has shown that objective range indicators, such as the
8 remaining driving range, are typically more decisive in user choices when both subjective and objective
9 range considerations are present (Franke, Rauh, and Krems 2016; Nazari, Mohammadian, and Stephens
10 2023), which could explain the decreased statistical significance of perceived range anxiety in this model.
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22 **6. Model Application**

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24 In this section, we contextualize the model findings by first examining the WTP indicators, which
25 quantify the trade-offs between specific attributes. Next, we conduct a scenario analysis to explore how
26 changes in key vehicle attributes influence decision-making and behavior, offering insights into the practical
27 implications of the model.
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33 *6.1. Willingness-to-Pay Indicators*

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35 WTP indicators translate the parameter estimates into actionable insights, helping to inform operational
36 decisions for EMSS operators. Since two random parameters were found to be significant, the WTP indica-
37 tors are distributed according to the random parameter distributions. Figure 4 provides an overview of all
38 WTP indicators affected by at least one random parameter, while Table 4 displays the two remaining WTP
39 indicators.
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46 The mean WTP for additional battery range based on the per-minute ride fee (see Figure 4a) is
47 €0.012/min for the ride fee, with a 95% quantile ranging from €0.005/min to €0.026/min. This sug-
48 gests that users value the extra battery capacity, but their valuation varies significantly. For example, if a
49 vehicle offers 3 km less range in a critical range situation, it must be on average €0.036 cheaper in per-minute
50 ride fee. Although due to its heterogeneity, this WTP indicator could range from a reduction of €0.015 to
51 €0.078 per-minute ride fee. Regarding the unlock fee, the WTP for additional battery (see Figure 4b) is
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€0.19, with a 95% quantile between €0.105 and €0.32. When comparing the mean reductions needed for the unlock fee and the per-minute ride fee on a 15-minute trip (driving time of 15 minutes), the reduction in the unlock fee (€0.57) is slightly higher than the total reduction in the ride fee (€0.54).

The mean WTP for a one minute reduction in walking time is slightly lower than reported by Hoobroeckx et al. (2023), who found a reduction of €0.02/min in the ride fee for each additional minute of walking. In our model, the WTP for a reduction in walking time (see Figure 4c) has a mean of €0.015/min, with the 95% quantile of the distribution ranging from €0.007/min to €0.028/min. For example, a e-moped located three minutes farther away must have an average reduction of €0.045/min of the ride fee to remain equally attractive. Due to the heterogeneity captured by the model, this WTP could vary widely, ranging from a reduction of only €0.021 up to €0.084 per-minute ride fee. When assuming a trip duration as pictured in the context (driving time of 15 minutes), this results in a total ride fee reduction of approximately €0.68. For the unlock fee, a reduction of €0.24 is needed per extra walking minute. This WTP is not dependent on a random parameter but is based on two fixed estimates. In the same example, a total reduction of €0.72 is required for an additional three minutes of walking, again being slightly higher than the total influence of the ride fee parameter.

Figure 4: Distributions of WTP for various factors derived from Hybrid Choice Model

Table 4: Willingness to Pay (WTP) for Various factors

Description	Value	Unit
WTP for reduction in walking (unlock fee)	0.24	€ for 1min
WTP for a faster vehicle (unlock fee)	0.72	€ for 45 km/h vehicle

Lastly, the WTP for a faster vehicle is considered. The mean WTP for a faster vehicle based on the ride fee (see Figure 4d) is €0.046/min, with a 95% quantile of the distribution between €0.022/min and €0.085/min. This quantifies the significant shift in preference, probably due to new helmet regulations (Rijksoverheid 2022). In contrast to previous studies reporting a preference for the slower vehicle type, the current preference for the faster type is as strong as a three-minute reduction in walking time. For the unlock fee, a reduction of €0.72 is required to make the slower vehicle type equally attractive.

In summary, the WTP indicators found that all included vehicle attributes significantly influence user preferences. It also highlighted how low remaining range impacts user preference in critical range situations, with considerable heterogeneity in its importance among users. The mandatory helmet regulations led to a preference shift toward faster vehicles, with a high willingness to pay for faster vehicles.

6.2. Scenario Analysis

This section describes and discusses the results derived from the scenario analysis as explained in Section 4.2.2. As we vary the non-price vehicle attributes against the price attributes, we first had to set the remaining variables to fixed values. To do this, we aimed to represent the average respondent as derived from the survey. Based on the respondent’s average characteristics mentioned in Section 5.1. These values resulted in a reflection of a typical EMSS user profile and potentially explain the high likelihood of choosing to use EMSS. To further put the results into perspective, it is important to note that the likelihood of choosing EMSS is also highly dependent on the context of the SP experiment, as explained in Section 3.1.1. These conditions favor the usage of EMSS, with favorable weather conditions, occasional trip patterns, and high availability of this service. In the following, we will discuss how varying the vehicle attributes influences this likelihood.

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3 6.2.1. Influence of remaining driving range on the likelihood of choosing EMSS
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6 In this first scenario analysis we explore how the likelihood of choosing a shared e-moped changes solely
7 based on varying the remaining driving range attribute, while other vehicle attributes remain fixed to reflect
8 current market prices and average walking distance, i.e. a walking distance of 5km, ride fee of €0.33 and a
9 unlock fee of €1 utilizing a 25km/h vehicle type. The results are illustrated in Figure 5. In this scenario,
10 the random parameter for the battery range is used, incorporating two curves that represent the lower and
11 upper 95% quantiles of the distribution.
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44 Figure 5: Likelihood of Choosing EMSS based on varying remaining range levels
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47 Figure 5 shows the significant influence of the remaining driving range on user preference. For instance,
48 at a remaining range of 5 km (equal to the trip length), the average likelihood of choosing an EMSS is
49 below 20%. However, this likelihood increases dramatically to over 60% when the remaining range reaches
50 14 km. This underscores the importance of addressing battery insufficiency, as it can lead users to opt out
51 of using an available e-moped. It also emphasizes the need for effective recharging strategies or mitigation
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3 measures. In addition to this, Figure 5 clearly illustrates the modeled heterogeneity in user preferences
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5 for the remaining battery range. For example, at a remaining range of 10 km (double the trip distance),
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7 the likelihood of choosing an e-moped varies significantly among individuals, ranging from below 20% in
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9 the lower quantile to above 80% in the upper quantile. This variation underscores the importance of
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11 considering user heterogeneity in vehicle choice. Although we aim to represent current market conditions,
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13 it is important to note that the absolute values of these likelihoods are highly dependent on the values of
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15 other vehicle attributes. Therefore, in the following sections, we will explore how varying these additional
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17 vehicle attributes influences the likelihood of choosing EMSS.
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21 *6.2.2. Influence of varying vehicle attributes on the likelihood of choosing EMSS*

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23 Figure 6 displays the likelihood of users choosing a EMSS based on varying combinations of three key
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25 vehicle attributes: remaining battery range, walking time to the vehicle, and the ride fee per minute. The
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27 two remaining vehicle attributes are set to €1 for the unlock fee and the slower vehicle type is used. The
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29 four heat maps visualize the likelihood of choosing EMSS over opting out for different levels of these three
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31 attributes as used in the survey, offering insights into how users respond to trade-offs between shorter walking
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33 time, cost, and the remaining range of the e-moped.
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36 Generally, the figure underlines the trends found in the model estimation results, that users are more
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38 likely to choose vehicles with higher remaining battery levels, shorter walking times, and lower ride fees. As
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40 the walking distance or prices increase or the battery range decreases, the likelihood of users opting for the
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42 service diminishes substantially. One of the key insights from the heat-maps is how the per-minute ride fee
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44 can compensate for less desirable vehicle attributes. For instance, vehicles with lower battery levels (e.g., 5
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46 km or 8 km) are far less attractive when paired with higher ride fees and longer walking distances. However,
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48 reducing the ride fee (e.g., from €0.33/min to €0.27/min) can significantly increase the likelihood of users
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50 choosing these less favorable vehicles. For example, at a 5 km remaining range and 1 minute of walking
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52 time, reducing the fee from €0.36/min to €0.27/min increases the likelihood of choosing EMSS from 23.9%
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54 to 76.0%. Similarly, the figure highlights that users are generally more tolerant of longer walking distances
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56 when the ride fee is low and the battery level is high. For example, at a battery range of 14 km and a ride
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3 fee of €0.27/min, even a walking time of 10 minutes results in a likelihood of 61.9%. In contrast, for the
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5 same 10-minute walk, if the ride fee is raised to €0.36/min, the likelihood drops to just 13.9%.
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7 A similar analysis was conducted utilizing the unlock fee as the price component fixing the ride fee to its
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9 current market price of €0.33/min. The full Figure of the four heat-maps can be found in [Appendix C](#). A
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11 notable difference between the two heat-maps is that the impact of the unlock fee appears to be slightly more
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13 significant for higher walking times and lower battery levels compared to the per-minute ride fee, resulting
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15 in an overall lower likelihood of choosing EMSS. However, the general pattern of user preferences remains
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17 consistent across both fee types, indicating that both ride fees and unlock fees can be strategically adjusted
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19 to manage vehicle distribution and utilization.
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22 This scenario analysis further highlights that operators can effectively mitigate the disutility of certain
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24 vehicle attributes by offering lower ride fees or unlock fees. However, this mitigation has its limits. While
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26 pricing strategies can help balance user preferences and optimize fleet utilization in shared e-moped services,
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28 certain factors, like battery range, remain critical. This scenario underscores again the pivotal role of battery
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30 range in user decisions. For example, even if a vehicle offers the lowest ride fee and is located 7 minutes
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32 away, its likelihood of being used is around 82% with a 14 km driving range. However, when the driving
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34 range drops to 5 km, this probability sharply decreases to just 28.6%.
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38 **7. Discussion and Managerial Insights**

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41 This section highlights key insights derived from our research, focusing on practical strategies for EMSS
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43 operators to enhance service efficiency and user satisfaction. The implications are based on the analysis of
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45 willingness-to-pay (WTP) indicators and the scenario analysis. Providing actionable recommendations for
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47 real-world applications. Further, the limitations of this research and potential directions for further research
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49 are discussed.
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52 *7.1. User-based relocation strategies through WTP Insights*

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55 Our findings suggest that even small price adjustments can significantly impact user behavior, particu-
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57 larly with respect to walking distance to access a vehicle. For example, reducing the ride fee by an average
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Figure 6: Likelihood of Choosing EMSS based on varying remaining range, walking time, and ride fee levels

of €0.015 per minute can incentivize users to walk an additional minute to reach a vehicle. Similarly, a €0.24 reduction in the unlock fee has a comparable effect. Considering the approximate ride time from the provided context, the total reduction for the ride fee amounts to €0.225. This highlights the similar influence on user preference of both pricing strategies. Therefore, our research further suggests that both ride fees and unlock fees are effective tools for operators to manage vehicle distribution and encourage users to access vehicles that are farther away. The price reductions needed derived from our study are even smaller than those reported by Hoobroeckx et al. (2023), further highlighting the potential effectiveness of user-based relocation strategies. By strategically lowering fees for vehicles placed in lower-demand areas, operators can balance vehicle availability across their service area, enhancing overall system efficiency.

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3 *7.2. Managing fleet utilization based on remaining driving range*
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5 While the analysis reveals that the latent variable on perceived range anxiety does not have a significant
6 influence on user preference, the remaining range vehicle attribute has a substantial influence with lower
7 ranges making vehicles less attractive. To mitigate this effect, operators can incentivize users to utilize
8 vehicles with lower remaining ranges. For example, a vehicle with 8km of remaining range and a ride fee of
9 €0.33/min can reach equal likelihood of being chosen then a vehicle with only 5km of remaining range with
10 a ride fee of €0.30/min. This strategy not only maximizes the use of the entire fleet but also helps prevent
11 vehicles from becoming stranded or underutilized due to low battery levels.
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20 However, it is important to note the significant heterogeneity in user preferences with respect to the
21 remaining driving range. Less experienced users may require higher incentives to choose vehicles with lower
22 battery levels. By offering customized incentives based on user experience and vehicle range, operators can
23 better manage their fleets and ensure a more balanced distribution of vehicles across different battery levels.
24 Additionally, rather than solely relying on price incentives to manage fleet utilization, EMSS operators can
25 also reduce range anxiety by providing enhanced information and user education. To effectively minimize
26 uncertainties and improve user confidence, operators can implement several actionable measures:
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35 **Enhanced Information Systems in the App:** EMSS operators can develop advanced interface
36 features in the user app that provide detailed information about each vehicle's range. This could include
37 visualizing how far the remaining range could potentially take the user (using a range circle) or allowing
38 users to input their destination to check if the remaining range is sufficient for the trip.
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43 **User Education and Training:** Educational content can be created within the app to guide users on
44 maximizing battery efficiency, understanding the reliability of remaining range estimates, and knowing what
45 to do if the battery runs out. This can help users feel more confident and informed when choosing vehicles
46 with lower remaining ranges.
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52 **Interface Features on Vehicles:** User-interface features can be incorporated directly into the vehicles
53 that provide detailed information about the remaining range and whether the destination is reachable. This
54 could involve displaying the remaining range in kilometers rather than just showing the state of charge as a
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3 percentage, offering detailed analytics on the expected range under different driving conditions, or integrating
4 a navigation system that compares the available range with the trip length, as present in modern BEVs.
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7 Lastly, while incentivizing users and mitigating range anxiety can optimize fleet utilization and improve
8 operational effectiveness, effective fleet management in terms of monitoring and balancing the remaining
9 range of vehicles is crucial to ensure service reliability and user satisfaction.
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11 12 13 *7.3. Adapting to Regulatory Changes in Vehicle Preferences*

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15 With the introduction of mandatory helmet regulations that standardize safety measures across different
16 vehicle types, there has been a noticeable shift in user preference towards faster vehicles. This presents
17 an opportunity for operators to adjust their pricing strategies accordingly. Based on WTP indicators,
18 it may be feasible to increase the fees for faster vehicles by between €0.022 and €0.084 per minute, or
19 by €0.71 in the unlock fee, without significantly deterring users. Operators should consider leveraging
20 these insights to optimize revenue while maintaining high user satisfaction. By aligning pricing with user
21 preferences for faster vehicles, they can better cater to market demand while ensuring compliance with safety
22 regulations. Another strategic focus could be on providing more 45 km/h vehicles, especially in scenarios
23 where competitive pricing should be maintained.
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37 *7.4. Limitations and Future Research*

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39 This study underlies certain limitations. First, the relatively small and highly educated sample may
40 introduce bias and limit the generalizability of the findings to the broader Dutch population, as discussed
41 in Section 5.1. While the inclusion of non-users offers insights into potential adoption patterns, their hy-
42 pothetical choices may not fully reflect actual behavior due to the inherent bias of SP experiments. The
43 study's reliance on a fixed context to simulate critical range situations may not capture the full variability of
44 real-world conditions, and factors like weather, trip purposes, and distances, which were controlled for, have
45 been shown to affect user preferences (Hoobroeckx et al. 2023). Consequently, the scenario analysis may
46 overestimate the likelihood of choosing EMSS, so emphasis should be placed on relative market share changes
47 rather than absolute values. Future research should increase sample size, incorporate revealed preference
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3 (RP) data, and include a more diverse respondent group to improve generalizability. Further, advanced
4 modeling techniques like latent class models could better capture user heterogeneity and the influence of
5 latent variables. Testing the operational implications in real-world settings is crucial to validate the findings
6 and ensure improved efficiency for EMSS providers.
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10 11 12 13 **8. Conclusion** 14 15

16 This study explored the key determinants of vehicle choice in electric moped sharing systems (EMSS),
17 focusing on both user-specific and vehicle-specific factors. It is among the first to investigate how range
18 anxiety influences user preferences in critical range situations, considering both the remaining battery range
19 and attitudinal factors such as perceived range anxiety. Additionally, the research assessed the effects of
20 new pricing strategies, like unlock fees, and regulatory changes, such as mandatory helmet laws. Using
21 a stated preference experiment and a Hybrid Choice Model (HCM), we quantified these effects to gain a
22 deeper understanding of user behavior.
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31 The findings reveal that users have a clear preference for lower fees, shorter walking distances, and vehi-
32 cles with higher remaining battery ranges. There is substantial heterogeneity in user preferences, particularly
33 concerning per-minute ride fees and battery range, indicating that these factors influence user decisions dif-
34 ferently across individuals. Some users are even willing to walk longer distances to access vehicles with more
35 favorable attributes. The introduction of mandatory helmet regulations has significantly shifted preferences
36 toward faster vehicles, demonstrating that regulatory interventions can substantially alter user behavior
37 and competitive dynamics within EMSS. Scenario analysis further illustrates how varying vehicle attributes
38 and pricing strategies affect market share and fleet utilization. Dynamic pricing, based on vehicle location,
39 emerges as a powerful tool for improving service availability and user satisfaction. Additionally, offering
40 incentives to use vehicles with lower battery levels can alleviate perceived disutility, encouraging continued
41 use even when battery levels are low. These insights are valuable for EMSS operators, enabling them to
42 tailor strategies that balance cost, convenience, and service availability, thereby optimizing fleet utilization
43 and enhancing user adoption in different contexts.
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3 **Appendix A. Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process**
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6 During the preparation of this work the author used generative AI tools in order to enhance readability
7 and ensure correct grammar and spelling. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content
8 as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.
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14 **Appendix B. Full set of parameter estimates for the HCM model**
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16 Table B.5: Model Fit indicators HCM

Metric	Value
Number of inter-individual draws	5000 (Halton)
LL(start)	-2421.42
LL(whole model) at equal shares, LL(0)	-2082.85
LL(whole model) at observed shares, LL(C)	-1711.64
LL(final, whole model)	-1410.67
Rho-squared vs equal shares	0.3227
Adj. Rho-squared vs equal shares	0.2978
Rho-squared vs observed shares	0.1758
Adj. Rho-squared vs observed shares	0.163
AIC	2925.33
BIC	3075.63
Estimated parameters	52

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34 Table B.6: Parameter Estimates for the HCM Model
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Parameter	Estimate	s.e.	t.rat.(0)	Rob. t.rat.(0)
$b_{Distance}$	-0.340	0.043	-7.941	-7.198
$b_{UnlockFee}$	-1.419	0.223	-6.364	-6.534
$b_{VehicleType}$	-1.023	0.211	-4.839	-5.165
$\mu_{RideFee}$	3.165	0.174	18.225	17.740
$\mu_{RemainingRange}$	-1.348	0.167	-8.094	-8.183
$\sigma_{RideFee}$	0.347	0.074	4.659	4.531
$\sigma_{RemainingRange}$	0.285	0.141	2.027	2.602
$b_{PreviousUse}$	-1.537	0.599	-2.565	-2.577
$b_{CarOwnership}$	0.533	0.561	0.951	0.972
$b_{BikeOwnership}$	-2.259	1.115	-2.025	-2.025
$b_{LivingAlone}$	1.197	0.463	2.586	2.810
$b_{SharedLiving}$	-0.814	0.438	-1.859	-1.945
$b_{LowIncome}$	-1.166	0.455	-2.562	-2.692
$b_{MediumIncome}$	-0.675	0.409	-1.651	-1.745

Table B.7: Latent Variable Parameter Estimates (Attitude towards EMSS) HCM

Parameter	Estimate	s.e.	t-rat.(0)	Robust t-rat.(0)
η_{emop}	0.9562	0.33877	2.8226	2.9909
$\tau_{emop_2^1}$	-5.9662	0.98447	-6.0603	-7.1000
$\tau_{emop_2^2}$	-4.4435	0.69229	-6.4185	-6.1353
$\tau_{emop_2^3}$	-2.4752	0.47386	-5.2235	-4.8614
$\tau_{emop_2^4}$	2.3803	0.47244	5.0383	5.4674
ζ_{emop_3}	1.1233	0.23421	4.7961	4.6865
$\tau_{emop_3^1}$	-3.0983	0.40298	-7.6884	-7.7241
$\tau_{emop_3^2}$	-1.4822	0.25587	-5.7925	-5.8927
$\tau_{emop_3^3}$	-0.4880	0.21977	-2.2206	-2.1459
$\tau_{emop_3^4}$	1.5980	0.26735	5.9771	6.2652
ζ_{emop_4}	1.2070	0.25523	4.7290	4.2245
$\tau_{emop_4^1}$	-5.5045	1.03468	-5.3200	-5.4272
$\tau_{emop_4^2}$	-3.2939	0.43227	-7.6200	-7.3553
$\tau_{emop_4^3}$	-0.9690	0.24145	-4.0132	-3.8831
$\tau_{emop_4^4}$	1.9817	0.30193	6.5635	6.2183

Table B.8: Latent Variable Parameter Estimates (Perceived range anxiety) HCM

Parameter	Estimate	s.e.	t-rat.(0)	Robust t-rat.(0)
$\eta_{rangaxi}$	-0.3141	0.32116	-0.9779	-0.9861
$\zeta_{rangaxi_1}$	2.3076	0.47116	4.8978	5.0846
$\tau_{rangaxi_1^1}$	-7.2612	1.34386	-5.4032	-4.6570
$\tau_{rangaxi_1^2}$	-3.8353	0.61481	-6.2382	-6.1279
$\tau_{rangaxi_1^3}$	-1.6188	0.38571	-4.1969	-4.2260
$\tau_{rangaxi_1^4}$	2.3508	0.44993	5.2248	5.3871
$\zeta_{rangaxi_2}$	1.8316	0.34335	5.3346	5.3445
$\tau_{rangaxi_2^1}$	-4.1686	0.58007	-7.1863	-6.6855
$\tau_{rangaxi_2^2}$	-1.6331	0.32903	-4.9634	-5.0056
$\tau_{rangaxi_2^3}$	-0.1300	0.26915	-0.4830	-0.4744
$\tau_{rangaxi_2^4}$	3.9395	0.55889	7.0488	7.3159
$\zeta_{rangaxi_4}$	3.9949	1.41356	2.8261	2.7989
$\tau_{rangaxi_4^1}$	-7.0612	2.11181	-3.3437	-3.2541
$\tau_{rangaxi_4^2}$	-4.0980	1.29746	-3.1584	-3.0684
$\tau_{rangaxi_4^3}$	-1.4068	0.63209	-2.2256	-2.1573
$\tau_{rangaxi_4^4}$	3.7952	1.21628	3.1204	3.1399

Appendix C. Scenario Analysis unlock fee

Figure C.7: Likelihood of Choosing EMSS based on varying remaining range, walking time, and unlock fee levels